

Timing of puberty in F1-generation hatchery-produced greater amberjack (*Seriola dumerili*)

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20 **Abstract**

22 We evaluated the onset of puberty of first-generation (F1) hatchery-produced greater
amberjack (*Seriola dumerili*) reared in sea cages for 5 years. Fish were sampled every year in
June, at the expected peak of the spawning period in the Mediterranean Sea. No sexual
24 dimorphism in body weight was observed in the study. The ovaries of 1 and 2-year-old (yo)
females consisted of primary oocytes only, while at the age of 3-yo early vitellogenic (Vg)
26 oocytes were also identified, but with extensive follicular atresia. At the age of 4-yo, late Vg
oocytes were observed, but again extensive follicular atresia characterized the ovaries of 50%
28 of females. At the age of 5-yo, follicular atresia of Vg oocytes was very limited. In males,
gametogenesis was evident already in 1- and 2-yo fish, and 100% of sampled 3-yo males
30 produced collectable viable sperm. Plasma testosterone (T), 17 β -estradiol (E2), and 17,20 β -
dihydroxy-4-pregnen-3-one (17,20 β -P) remained similar in 3 – 5-yo females, with T and E2
32 levels being highest in females in advanced vitellogenesis or with significant follicular atresia,
compared to immature females. In males, plasma T declined over the years, while 11-
34 ketotestosterone (11-KT) and 17,20 β -P were highest in 4 and 5-yo males, with spermatozoa
motility characteristics being improved from the 4th year onwards. The administration of
36 GnRH α implants to 5-yo fish induced only two spawns, albeit no fertilized eggs were obtained.
The results indicate that hatchery-produced greater amberjack males mature well and within
38 the same age observed in the wild, however with smaller gonad size. On the contrary, females
mature later than in the wild, also with a smaller gonad size. Spawning in response to GnRH α
40 treatment was not effective, suggesting that Mediterranean hatchery-produced broodstocks
may be dysfunctional, and further research is needed to document any improvement as the fish
42 get older, or to determine if the results may be related to the specific stock of fish.

44 **Keywords:** Greater amberjack, *Seriola dumerili*, puberty, spawning induction, GnRH α

46 **Highlights**

1. No sexual size dimorphism was observed in up to 5-year-old greater amberjack

48 2. Puberty occurred in 3-year-old hatchery-produced male greater amberjack

3. Puberty occurred in 5-year-old hatchery-produced female greater amberjack

50 4. Gonadal size was significantly smaller than mature, reproductively active fish in the wild

5. Spawning induction with GnRH α was not effective, suggesting a dysfunction in females

52

1. Introduction

54 Puberty has been defined as the transitional period occurring after sex differentiation,
during which the brain-pituitary-gonad (BPG) axis of immature individuals acquires
56 competence and functionality (Taranger et al., 2010). In teleosts, spermatogenesis in males
(Almeida et al., 2016; Schulz and Miura, 2002) and vitellogenesis in females (Patiño and
58 Sullivan, 2002; Sullivan and Yilmaz, 2018) are mostly used to mark the onset of puberty
(Schulz and Nóbrega, 2011), whereas its ending point would be the acquisition of the ability
60 to reproduce for the first time, *i.e.* to produce fertile gametes (Okuzawa, 2002).

Exogenous factors, such as temperature, photoperiod and nutrition, as well as
62 endogenous factors, such as somatic growth and sex steroid hormones, have been proposed to
stimulate the BPG axis during puberty (Migaud et al., 2010; Mylonas et al., 2010; Zohar et al.,
64 2010). The alteration of one or more of these factors may lead to a shift in the timing of puberty
(Avella et al., 2012; Passini et al., 2019; Rodríguez et al., 2000). Acquiring insights into the
66 process of puberty and the age at which a species acquires full reproductive functionality is of
primary importance for the commercial farming of any species. The onset of puberty is one of
68 the most significant stages in the species' lifecycle, and under aquaculture conditions,
precocious or late occurrence of puberty can impact greatly commercial production -both
70 positively and negatively. For instance, in the well-established aquaculture species the
European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) (Felip et al., 2006; Papadaki et al., 2005) and Atlantic
72 salmon (*Salmo salar*) (Crouse et al., 2022), precocious maturation can inhibit growth, increase
the size of the gonad and affect negatively the organoleptic properties of the flesh, thus leading
74 to economic losses at harvesting (McClure et al., 2007). On the contrary, in species with late
puberty, such as the Atlantic bluefin tuna (*Thunnus thynnus*) (Berkovich et al., 2013; Corriero
76 et al., 2003) and striped bass (*Morone saxatilis*) (Holland et al., 2000), maintaining a
broodstock for several years before it reaches maturity might build up excessive costs (*i.e.*

78 feeding, labor and facilities) (Higuchi et al., 2017), and also delay the implementation of
selective breeding programs.

80 The greater amberjack (*Seriola dumerili*) is a cosmopolitan species, distributed in
temperate and subtropical waters (Jerez et al., 2006; Marino et al., 1995; Nyuji et al., 2016).
82 Because of its numerous attractive flesh characteristics (Alexi et al., 2020; Mazzola et al.,
2000), greater amberjack is easily marketable and appreciated by consumers worldwide
84 (Nijssen et al., 2019). Therefore, it has gripped the interest of the Mediterranean aquaculture
industry. This fish is a seasonal spawner and its reproductive season lies between spring and
86 summer, even though the timing and extension of spawning might differ according to the
environmental conditions of different geographical areas (Jerez et al., 2006; Wells and Rooker,
88 2004). In the Mediterranean Sea, early spawns are recorded at the end of May when the sea
surface temperature reaches 19-20°C, although it is when temperatures increase to 23-24°C in
90 June-July that gonads are found fully mature in most adult fish, and the spawning season peaks
(Pousis et al., 2018).

92 Although much information on the reproductive physiology of greater amberjack is
available in the scientific literature, most of the studies have used fish sampled in the wild or
94 wild-caught captivity-reared fish. Wild-caught greater amberjack breeders adapt to
aquaculture conditions and grow rapidly, but they have been shown to exhibit reproductive
96 dysfunctions and hormonal imbalances in both sexes (Corriero et al., 2021a; Corriero et al.,
2021b; Fakriadis et al., 2019; Micale et al., 1999; Mylonas et al., 2004). The development of
98 hatchery-produced breeders is essential for the sustainability of the aquaculture industry, as
domesticated stocks may be better adapted to the captive environment. In addition, breeding
100 selection programs require hatchery-produced breeders that are able to reproduce under
captivity. Therefore, it is imperative to (a) study the timing of puberty of hatchery-produced

102 greater amberjack and (b) evaluate the reproductive function of these fish, when they reach
puberty.

104 Data on sex steroid levels of greater amberjack are limited, focused mainly on describing
changes in adult fish during the reproductive season and obtained, once more, mostly from
106 wild or wild-caught reared fish. Moreover, reported steroid levels have been so far restricted
to the most common androgens and estrogens, namely testosterone (T), 11-ketotestosterone
108 (11-KT), and 17 β -estradiol (E2) (Mandich et al., 2004; Zupa et al., 2017a; Zupa et al., 2017b).
Recently, some studies have been conducted on hatchery-produced greater amberjack. For
110 instance, in the Canary Islands (Spain), an F1 broodstock was used in spawning experiments
(Jerez et al., 2018), where levels of sex steroids were found to be lower compared to fish in the
112 wild, but similar to captive-reared wild fish. In Greece, sex differentiation was described in a
hatchery-produced greater amberjack stock (Papadaki et al., 2021). The authors suggested the
114 involvement of 11-KT as the male-specific hormone participating in the sex differentiation of
greater amberjack, and androgens (adrenosterone, androstenedione, testosterone and 11-KT)
116 and progestogens (progesterone and 17,20 β -dihydroxy-4-pregnen-3-one) were considered as
regulators of the process in both sexes (Papadaki et al., 2021). Here, we were interested in
118 examining the levels of these hormones during the gonadal development of hatchery-produced
greater amberjack over the years, and their possible role in the initiation of puberty.

120 The present work aimed to examine the onset of puberty and the relevant physiological
and endocrine changes in a hatchery-produced greater amberjack stock. To do so, biometrical
122 parameters, gonadal development, as well as the hormonal profile of various sex steroid
hormones in the blood were examined for five consecutive reproductive seasons, in fish
124 maintained in sea cages. During the last two reproductive seasons, gonadotropin-releasing
hormone agonist (GnRH α) was administered in an attempt to induce spawning in 4 and 5-yo
126 fish, and to evaluate reproductive performance.

128 **2. Materials and methods**

2.1. Ethical statement

130 The experimental protocol was approved by the National Veterinary Services
(AP31326). All procedures involving animals were conducted in accordance with the
132 “Guidelines for the treatment of animals in behavioral research and teaching” (Anonymous,
1998), the Ethical justification for the use and treatment of fishes in research: an update
134 (Metcalf and Craig, 2011) and the “Directive 2010/63/EU of the European parliament and the
council of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes” (EU,
136 2010).

138 **2.2. Fish and rearing conditions**

In June 2017, greater amberjack eggs were obtained from wild-caught breeders induced
140 to spawn with GnRH α implants in Argosaronikos Fish Farm S.A. (Salamina Island, Greece)
(Fakriadis et al., 2020a). Eggs were transferred to the facilities of the Institute of Marine
142 Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture (IMBBC) of the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research
(HCMR, Registration NoEL91-BIObr-03, and EL91-BIOexp-04), and hatched larvae were
144 reared until 50 days post-hatching. Then, the fingerlings were divided into two batches. The
first one was transferred and maintained in grow-out cages (6 x 6 m) at the pilot sea cage farm
146 of HCMR (Souda Bay, Chania, Crete, Greece, GR94FISH0001) (Papadaki et al., 2021) and
was used as the 1-yo population of the present study. The second batch was transferred to
148 Argosaronikos Fishfarms S.A, where it was maintained in sea cages for five years and was
used for the subsequent years’ samplings. The temperature of surface seawater was measured
150 at least once a week from October 2017 to June 2022, and it ranged between 13.5 and 29°C
during the years (Fig. 1) and between 18.5 and 26°C in June, during the usual spawning

152 induction period. Fish were fed to apparent satiation with a commercial feed (Vitalis Repro,
Skretting, Spain) five times a week.

154

2.3. Blood, gonad sampling, and hormonal spawning induction

156 Fish were sampled once a year in June, when the natural reproductive season of greater
amberjack in the Mediterranean basin reaches its peak (Fakriadis et al., 2020a; Mandich et al.,
158 2004; Marino et al., 1995; Pousis et al., 2019), over a period of five years (2018-2022). In June
2018, 17 fish of the 1-yo population were anesthetized with phenoxy-ethanol for blood
160 collection and then killed in an overdose of the anesthetic bath. Total length (TL, cm) and
body weight (BW, g) were measured, and gonads were collected for histology. After
162 sacrificing the fish, macroscopical examination of the gonads allowed for sex identification in
15 of the collected fish (8 males and 7 females), the blood samples of which were used for
164 subsequent plasma sex steroid concentration measurements (Papadaki et al., 2021).

From 2019 to 2021, prior to each sampling, 2- 3-, and 4-yo fish were sedated at a dose
166 of 0.01 ml l⁻¹ clove oil in a 15-m³ sedation sack placed inside the sea cage and then transferred
individually in a 1 m³-tank at a dose of 0.03 ml l⁻¹ of clove oil for full anesthesia (Mylonas et
168 al., 2005). Biopsies were collected to sex the fish before dissection, in order to obtain an equal
number of specimens of both sexes. Once the established number of fish (n = 6) for each sex
170 was obtained, subsequent fish of the same sex were transferred back to the cage. Blood samples
were collected, and BW, TL, and gonad weight (GW, g) were measured after euthanizing with
172 a lethal dose of anesthetic, followed by a post-cranial section of the spinal cord and dissection
of the fish. The GW was used later to calculate the gonadosomatic index (GSI; [GW/BW]
174 x100). Due to severe weather conditions, in 2019 the sampling was interrupted as the
operations were conducted on a platform nearby the cages. At this sampling point, it was not
176 possible to collect blood, and a reduced number of samples was obtained (n=2 males, n=4

females) for histological evaluation of the gonads. Data for TL and GSI of 5-yo fish were not
178 obtained in 2022, since no fish were sacrificed at this stage. It was considered unnecessary for
the purpose of the study, and there was a need to maintain an adequate number of breeding
180 individuals for the future commercial purposes of the company.

From the third year of age (2020), fish were evaluated for spawning eligibility. For
182 spawning induction, only females having fully vitellogenic oocytes of $>600\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter
were used, and males that were in spermiation and sperm could be obtained for evaluation.
184 Ovarian biopsies were collected using a catheter (Pipelle de Cornier, Laboratoire CCD, France)
inserted into the ovary through the genital pore, and then applying gentle suction. The biopsies
186 were evaluated (a) under a microscope at 4x and 10x magnification in order to select females
for spawning induction and then (b) through histological processing (see later). Collected
188 gonads and biopsies were preserved in a solution of 4% formaldehyde: 1% glutaraldehyde for
histological analysis. Stripping of sperm using abdominal pressure was not possible due to the
190 thick muscular abdominal structure of greater amberjack (Fakriadis and Mylonas, 2021).
Therefore, sperm for quality evaluation was also collected using a biopsy catheter (Pipelle de
192 Cornier, Laboratoire CCD, France) inserted into the genital pore and then applying gentle
suction. Sperm samples (100-200 μL) were stored at 4°C until analyzed using computer-
194 assisted sperm analysis (CASA, see later).

At each sampling time, from the third to the fifth year of the study, blood was collected
196 from the caudal vein using heparinized syringes and after collection, it was centrifuged at 4500
rpm for 15 min at $+4^{\circ}\text{C}$. The obtained plasma was maintained at -80°C until hormonal analysis
198 using liquid chromatography tandem mass spectroscopy (LC-MS/MS).

200 **2.4 Spawning induction**

Some 4-yo and 5-yo fish were considered capable of spawning and were selected
202 according to their reproductive stage, as explained above, for spawning induction. They were
administered implants of ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymer (EVAc) (Mylonas et al., 2007;
204 Zohar and Mylonas, 2001) loaded with Des-Gly¹⁰, D-Ala⁶-Pro-NEth⁹-mGnRHa (H-4070,
Bachem, Switzerland). After GnRHa treatment, fish were transferred to a 25-m³ (2021;
206 females: n=4, 9.4±0.9 kg; males: n=4, 8.1±0.3 kg) or a 75-m³ (2022; females: n=5, 10.7±0.9
kg; males=7, 10.3±0.7) round tank for spawning, and reproductive performance was evaluated
208 (see later). The effective GnRHa dose was 69 ± 11 µg GnRHa kg⁻¹ in 2021 and 66 ± 4 µg
GnRHa kg⁻¹ in 2022. The tanks were covered and were supplied with surface seawater at
210 ambient temperature (Fig. 1)) at a water renewal of 400-500% day. The fish were exposed to
a natural photoperiod through large windows in the building where the 25-m³ tank was located,
212 or through openings in the plastic cover of the outside 75-m³ tank.

214 **2.5 Histological analysis**

The dissected gonads of all the sampled fish were dehydrated in a 70-95% ethanol series
216 and embedded in glycol methacrylate resin (Technovit 7100, Heraeus Kulzer, Germany). Serial
sections of 4 µm of the gonadal tissue were obtained using a semi-automatic microtome (Leica
218 RM2245, Germany). Histology slides were stained with methylene blue/azure II/basic fuchsin
(Bennet, 1976) and examined under a light microscope (50i Eclipse, Nikon, Japan). Eventually,
220 microphotographs of the stained tissues were taken using a digital camera (Progres, Jenoptik
AG, Germany).

222

2.6 Measurement of plasma sex steroids

224 The extraction and analysis of steroid hormones were performed according to Papadaki
et al. (2021) with a few modifications. The following sex steroids were included in the panel

226 of analytes: T, estrone (E1), E2, 11-KT and 17 α ,20 β -dihydroxy-4-pregnen-3-one (17,20 β -P).
Furthermore, instead of N,N-dimethyl-L-phenylalanine, 13C-labelled estradiol, testosterone,
228 and progesterone (>98% purity) purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories Inc
(Tewksbury, MA, USA), were used as internal standards for better quality control and more
230 accurate quantification of hormones. A mixture of those compounds in varying concentrations
(10 to 85 pg μ L⁻¹) was prepared in methanol: water 1:1 and 10 μ L of this solution was added
232 to the serum samples prior to solid phase extraction. Subsequently, the preparation of samples
and the analysis of hormones by LC-MS/MS was implemented following the same procedures
234 as those described in our previous study.

236 2.7 Sperm quality analysis

For sperm quality analysis using CASA (ISAS, Spain), milt from each sampled male (3-
238 yo in 2020, n=2; 4-yo in 2021, n=10; and 5-yo in 2022, n=8) was activated in seawater (1:201
or 1:334) containing 2% bovine serum albumin to obtain 200–300 cells in the field. A re-usable
240 counting chamber with a fixed depth (SpermTrack) was used to record spermatozoa movement
using a digital camera at 100 frames per second (fps) attached to a light microscope (Zeiss
242 Primo Star, Germany) under 100 \times magnification. The analysis included the following
parameters: sperm density (number of spermatozoa ml⁻¹ of milt), duration of forward
244 spermatozoa motility until 5% of the spermatozoa in the field of view were motile (motility
duration, min), curvilinear velocity (VCL), straight-line velocity (VSL), average path velocity
246 (VAP) (μ m sec⁻¹), motile cells, progressive cells (> 80% straightness, STR), rapid cells and
STR (%). The software settings were adjusted to 1 to 90 μ m for the head area; VCL < 10 μ m
248 sec⁻¹ to classify a spermatozoon as immotile; and spermatozoa were considered rapid when
VCL was higher than 100 μ m sec⁻¹.

250

2.8 Reproductive performance evaluation

252 Following spawning induction in 4-yo and 5-yo greater amberjack, fish were kept in the
tank for 14 days for spawning. A semi-conical egg collector tank (1-2 m³) fitted with a 300-
254 µm mesh cylinder was connected to the water overflow of the broodstock tanks and checked
twice a day (8.00 a.m. and 8.00 p.m.). Egg production was evaluated through the estimation
256 of daily fecundity (number of eggs) and fertilization success (%). Spawned eggs were taken
from the egg collector and placed into a 10-l bucket, from which a sub-sample of 10 ml was
258 taken with a plastic pipette for egg counting and quality estimation. All eggs contained in the
sub-sample were counted using a stereoscope (Zeiss Stemi 305, Germany) and checked for
260 fertilization success immediately after collection. Fertilized eggs are then incubated in a 1-m³
conical incubator supplied with sand-filtered (10 µm) and UV-treated surface seawater at
262 ambient temperature (Fig. 1).

264 2.9 Statistical analysis

Differences in BW, TL, and GSI were tested using a two-way Analysis of Variance
266 (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Due to high variability among individuals as
well as between the different classes of age, in order to avoid type I errors due to the violation
268 of the assumption of homogeneity of variances, hormonal profiles of sex steroids over time in
females and males, as well as levels of steroids by reproductive stage, were analyzed using
270 Welch's Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnett's T3 post hoc test. Sperm
quality parameters were analyzed using Kruskal-Wallis followed by Dunn's post hoc test.
272 Results are presented as mean values ± standard error of the mean (SEM) unless mentioned
otherwise. In all the statistical tests performed, p-values below 0.05 were considered
274 statistically significant. Statistical analyses were run using GraphPad Prism 9.4.1 for Mac OS,
GraphPad Software, San Diego, California USA, www.graphpad.com.

276

3. Results

278 3.1. Growth and gonadal development

The BW of the fish increased during the first 4 years of the study, but remained
280 unchanged in the 5th year, with no differences detected between sexes (Fig. 2a). The mean
(\pm SEM) final BW of 5-yo males and females reached $10,300 \pm 736$ g and $10,670 \pm 869$ g,
282 respectively. The TL of males and females also did not differ, and increased significantly for
the first 4 years (Fig. 2b). The GSI increased significantly over time with mean values of 2.3
284 $\pm 0.5\%$ and $3.0 \pm 1.2\%$ in 4-yo males and females, respectively (Fig. 2c).

In 1-yo fish, ovaries contained a predominant population of primary oocytes with
286 oogonia interspersed among them (Figs. 3a and 5a). One year later, all 2-yo female gonads
were found to be constituted by primary oocytes at the perinuclear stage (Figs. 3b and 5a). At
288 3 years of age, the gonadal development of females was more variable (Figs. 3c-d, and 5a).
Primary oocytes were the only germ cell population in 17% of the sampled females, whereas
290 oocyte growth reached early vitellogenesis in 33% of the females, exhibiting negligible levels
of atresia (Figs. 3c and 5a). The remaining 3-yo females showed oocytes in extensive atresia
292 surrounding primary and cortical alveoli oocytes (Figs. 3d and 5a). Following an earlier
classification (Hunter and Macewicz, 1985), yolked oocytes at the alpha (α) stage of atresia
294 were visible throughout the histological sections. Nuclear disappearance, coalescence of yolk
material, and fragmentation of zona radiata were distinctive signs of the process. A
296 comparable, yet not identical, reproductive status was found in the 4-yo females. A high
percentage (33%) did not initiate vitellogenesis at all, whereas only 17% were found to be in
298 an advanced stage of vitellogenesis (Figs. 3e and 5a). The remaining 50% of the females
presented diffuse atretic activity among vitellogenic follicles (Fig. 5a). Along with α -stage
300 atretic oocytes exhibiting disrupted membranes and disorganization of cytoplasmic contents,

some oocytes underwent complete degradation entering β -stage atresia (Fig. 3f). At this stage,
302 atretic follicles appeared as masses of unorganized vacuoles with completely digested
membranes, surrounded by blood vessels. Eventually, in all 5-yo females all stages typical of
304 vitellogenesis were detected (Figs. 3g-h, and 5a). At this age, atresia was present only at low
and physiological levels (Corriero et al., 2021b).

306 Regarding the males, 25% of dissected testes from 1-yo fish were immature, containing
only spermatogonia (Figs. 4a and 5b). Early (Fig. 4a) or advanced spermatogenesis was
308 detected in a few cysts in the remaining 1-yo fish, with spermatocytes, spermatids and
spermatozoa all being detected in the gonads together with spermatogonia (Fig. 5b). Although
310 in 2-yo males spermatogenic activity was present, spermatogonia still constituted the main
population of germ cells in 50% of the males (Figs. 4b and 5b). On the contrary, the testicular
312 lumen of the remaining 50% of males was found filled with large numbers of spermatozoa as
well as many spermatocysts with developing germ cells (Figs. 4c and 5b). Both in 3-yo and 4-
314 yo males, the testes exhibited a testicular lumen filled with spermatozoa (Figs. 4c and d), with
50 and 35% of males, respectively, being in an arrested state of spermatogenesis with only a
316 few residual developing spermatocysts in the germinal epithelium (Figs. 4d and 5b).

318 **3.2. Sex steroid plasma levels**

Significant changes in the sex steroid profile of both sexes were found over the course of
320 the experiment (Figs. 6 and 7). Differences were detected in the levels of E1 in females and T,
11-KT, E2, and 17,20 β -P in males. In females, the highest levels of E1 were in 3- and 4-yo
322 fish and decreased sharply in 5-yo females. In males, T, and E2 reached maximum
concentrations in 3-yo fish, dropping thereafter in 5-yo fish. On the contrary, plasma levels of
324 11-KT and 17,20 β -P reached maximum concentrations in 4- and 5-yo males, at the time of the
greatest number of males in full spermiation. Plasma levels of sex steroids were also examined

326 in relation to the reproductive stage of females, regardless of their age, due to the variability
observed in the reproductive stage among similarly aged individuals. The concentration of T
328 values rose markedly in atretic females, while being similar to vitellogenic individuals (Fig.
8a). Plasma E2 concentration of vitellogenic and atretic females was significantly higher than
330 immature ones (Fig. 8b).

332 **3.3. Sperm quality evaluation**

In 3-yo males, spermatozoa concentration ranged between $45 - 51 \times 10^9$ spermatozoa ml^{-1} , being
334 on average $48 \pm 4 \times 10^9$ spermatozoa ml^{-1} , and was statistically lower when compared to 4-yo males, of
which spermatozoa concentration values varied between $65 - 144 \times 10^9$ spermatozoa ml^{-1} with a mean
336 value of $95 \pm 9 \times 10^9$ (Fig. 9a). Spermatozoa concentration was slightly lower in 5-yo males.
There was a large individual variability observed in the measured sperm quality parameters
338 among fish of the same age class, with percentages of motile, progressive and rapid cells
differing at times by 40%, although no statistically significant differences in the mean values
340 were found among years (Fig. 9b). The ability of the progressive cells to move on a straight
trajectory was less variable, with mean STR being $89 \pm 5.3\%$ in 3-yo males, and $91 \pm 0.8\%$ or
342 $93 \pm 0.8\%$ in 4- and 5-yo fish, respectively. Still, no significant difference was observed among
different aged males (Fig. 9b). Finally, the parameters related to the velocity of the analyzed
344 milt, such as VCL, VSL, and VAP, also did not differ significantly among years (Fig. 9c).

346 **3.4. Spawning performance**

In 4-yo fish, no spawning was observed after treatment with GnRH α . The next year, a
348 total of two spawning events were recorded in 5-yo breeders (Fig. 10). The first spawn
occurred 72 h after the GnRH α administration, while the second occurred 7 days later. Total
350 production was 389,000 eggs, with a daily relative fecundity of 6,710 and 488 eggs kg^{-1} female

BW in the first and the second spawn, respectively. Fertilization success was 0% in both
352 spawns (Fig. 10), therefore no egg incubation was attempted.

354 **4. Discussion**

Following the description of the process of sex differentiation (Papadaki et al., 2021),
356 here we continued with the monitoring of the onset of puberty in first-generation (F1) hatchery-
produced greater amberjack reared in sea cages. We then evaluated their response to GnRHa-
358 induction of spawning using previously established methodologies for wild-caught captive-
reared broodstocks (Fakriadis et al., 2020a; Fakriadis et al., 2020b; Mylonas et al., 2010).
360 Spawning attempts were carried out in June, based on previous findings indicating that greater
amberjack in the Mediterranean Sea reaches maximal reproductive development and spawn
362 between May and July (Pousis et al., 2018; Zupa et al., 2017b).

The onset of puberty and the age of first maturity of hatchery-produced greater amberjack
364 has not been described so far, and it is essential for building up a reliable aquaculture
production strategy for this species. According to the existing data, the greater amberjack is a
366 late-maturing species with relative plasticity in the timing of puberty, which may depend on
sampling location and environmental conditions (Harris et al., 2007; Kozul et al., 2001; Marino
368 et al., 1995). Moreover, due to the different criteria adopted to define the first age of maturity,
there are noticeable discrepancies in the published information. For instance, specimens from
370 the Southeastern U.S.A. Atlantic coast and the Gulf of Gabes with developing, ripe or spent
gonads were all considered sexually mature (Harris et al., 2007; Sley et al., 2014). In addition,
372 considering mature females, individuals with the most advanced oocytes being at the cortical
alveoli stage, likely produced bias in estimating the numbers of spawning-capable individuals,
374 and the age and size of first maturity.

In our study, no sexual dimorphism in growth rate was found until the fish's 5th year of
376 life, in agreement with the work conducted on hatchery-produced greater amberjack during
their first year of life (Papadaki et al., 2021). Sexual size dimorphism was reported in wild
378 greater amberjack from the Western Atlantic and was attributed either to a longer life span in
one of the sexes (Thompson et al., 1999), or to an adaptation of mature females to maximize
380 fecundity (Harris et al., 2007). Therefore, contradictory information exists on sexual
dimorphism of size, which may be related to differences between rearing in the wild and in
382 captivity.

As regards gonadal development, a steady increase over the years was evident in the GSI
384 of both sexes with no differences between them, even though complete sexual maturation was
achieved in different ages in the two sexes. Comparing our results with fish of a similar age
386 and BW (≥ 9 kg) sampled during the spawning period (June-July) in the wild, the mean GSI
values of both males and females of the present study ($\sim 3\%$) were lower than fish in the wild
388 ($\geq 4.5\%$), but higher than wild-caught captive-reared individuals ($\sim 1\%$) (Zupa et al., 2017a;
Zupa et al., 2017b). This was a positive result, suggesting that the growth of the gonad in F1
390 individuals was better than in wild-caught juveniles reared in captivity, perhaps due to better
adaptation of the hatchery-produced individuals.

392 The histological assessment of reproductive development in the present study showed
that Vg oocytes appeared first in 3-yo females, similar to results obtained from the wild, as
394 well as with captive-reared individuals (Kozul et al., 2001), but in a larger fraction of
individuals than in the wild (Marino et al., 1995). Unfortunately, extensive follicular atresia
396 was also observed in 50% of the ovaries of both 3- and 4-yo females. The same condition was
reported in two different studies on captive-reared wild fish (Micale et al., 1999; Zupa et al.,
398 2017b); the authors reported that follicular atresia became the dominant process visible once
the oocytes reached the late stage of secondary growth (vitellogenesis). In some teleost fishes,

400 an incomplete gametogenic cycle might occur, referred to as a "dummy run" (Holland et al.,
2000; Papadaki et al., 2018), before puberty and the completion of reproductive maturation.
402 This may happen in wild fish due to a multiplicity of factors, such as poor environmental
conditions and availability of food, while in hatchery-reared fish, as most likely in this study,
404 it may happen due to partial incompetence of the BPG axis (Corriero et al., 2021b; Zmora et
al., 2014). Eventually, late Vg oocytes were found in the ovaries of 5-yo females that were
406 considered spawning-capable and eligible for hormonal induction, in the present study.
Although follicular atresia was still present, its frequency was considered typical of multiple
408 spawners during the spawning season (Bromley et al., 2000; Corriero et al., 2021b), suggesting
that these F1 females finally reached full reproductive capacity.

410 In F1 hatchery-produced males, on the other hand, testes with spermatocysts showing
spermatozoa were found since the first year of the study and increased gradually over time.
412 However, males were considered fully mature when they were 3-yo, when there was evidence
of large numbers of free spermatozoa in the testicular lumen (Almeida et al., 2016). While in
414 the Mediterranean Sea the age of first sexual maturity for wild males was considered to occur
in the 4th year of life (Marino et al., 1995), in the Atlantic Ocean 99% of 3-yo individuals
416 completed gametogenesis (Harris et al., 2007), corroborating our results. To date, from the
limited data available on the characteristics and the quality of sperm in greater amberjack, what
418 does seem evident is that captive conditions also hamper the development of the testes, leading
to a consequent reduction of sperm quality (Zupa et al., 2017a). Therefore, starting from the
420 age of first maturity that was identified as the 3rd year of life in the present study, milt was also
collected to further evaluate the reproductive capacity of F1 hatchery-produced greater
422 amberjack. A recent study provided valuable information on spermiation and sperm quality in
wild-caught greater amberjack reared in sea cages before being transferred to tanks during the
424 reproductive period (Fakriadis and Mylonas, 2021). In that study, before males were treated

for spawning induction, mean values for velocity-related parameters -namely, VCL and VSL-
426 did not exceed 100 and 70 $\mu\text{m sec}^{-1}$, respectively. In comparison, sperm collected from F1
males in the present study had mean VCL and VSL higher than 120 and 100 $\mu\text{m sec}^{-1}$,
428 respectively. Likewise, the mean values of VAP of F1 males surpassed those of captive-reared
wild males recorded during the spawning season (Fakriadis and Mylonas, 2021; Zupa et al.,
430 2017a). Regarding the mean values of motile, progressive and rapid cells, as well as for STR,
no evidence of differences was found among fish of different age classes. As much as it may
432 appear as a contradiction when compared to captive-reared wild fish, 3-yo males displayed
similar values, while on the other hand, the percentage of spermatozoa classified as progressive
434 and rapid from 4- and 5-yo F1 males was two-fold higher than wild-caught captive-reared
males (Fakriadis and Mylonas, 2021). The limited number of sperm samples available from
436 3-yo males might be accountable for this discrepancy and might have made existing changes
in sperm quality parameters in relation to age in the current study, undetectable. Finally,
438 concerning the concentration of spermatozoa, in 3-yo males it was comparable to those of
captive-reared wild fish, but increased in the following reproductive seasons and surpassed that
440 of captive-reared wild fish in other studies (Fakriadis and Mylonas, 2021; Fakriadis et al.,
2020b; Zupa et al., 2017a) as well as of that of F1 males from the Atlantic Ocean (Jerez et al.,
442 2018). Unfortunately, no data on sperm quality parameters of greater amberjack or any other
congener are available from the wild, making it impossible to determine the optimal values for
444 these studied parameters presented here.

The acquisition of competence of the BPG axis is pivotal to reaching sexual maturity, as
446 its full activation leads to the production of gonadal steroids, which are responsible for the
initiation and completion of the gametogenic cycle (Carrillo et al., 2009; Chakraborty et al.,
448 2011; Lubzens et al., 2010; Nagahama and Yamashita, 2008; Taranger et al., 2010). Therefore,
steroids such as E2, T, 11-KT, 17,20 β -P and 17,20 β ,21-trihydroxy-4-pregnen-3-one

450 (17,20 β ,21-P) have been used as reliable markers to discern the reproductive status in fish
(Mylonas et al., 2013; Zohar and Mylonas, 2001), including the greater amberjack (Mandich
452 et al., 2004). However, the same seasonal elevations, both in amplitude and duration, observed
in plasma levels of sex steroids in wild greater amberjack (Mandich et al., 2004; Zupa et al.,
454 2017b) and its congener yellowtail kingfish (*Seriola lalandi*) (Poortenaar et al., 2001) were not
evident in captive-reared wild-caught greater amberjack, in which farming conditions
456 seemingly affected gonadal steroidogenesis (Zupa et al., 2017b). Likewise, in the monitored
F1 females, overall low and unchanged levels of T and E2 were found, aligned with those of
458 captive-reared fish from previous studies (Jerez et al., 2018; Nyuji et al., 2016; Zupa et al.,
2017b). Also, plasma levels of 17,20 β -P were found to be a good indicator of oocyte
460 maturation in the yellowtail kingfish and in wild greater amberjack (Mandich et al., 2004;
Poortenaar et al., 2001). However, in F1 greater amberjack in the Atlantic Ocean, plasma
462 levels of 17,20 β -P remained unchanged after GnRH α induction of spawning (Jerez et al., 2018).
In the examined F1 females of the present study, no differences in the plasma levels of 17,20 β -
464 P were observed over the years. These results may be because of the rapid metabolism of this
steroid (Scott et al., 2010), or due to the fact that at the sampling time, no fish were observed
466 to have oocytes undergoing oocyte maturation.

To further expand our investigation, plasma levels were also correlated with specific
468 ovarian stages rather than solely with the age of females. Elevated T and E2 concentrations
were evident in females undergoing vitellogenesis compared to less developed females,
470 indicating that although the recorded concentrations were considerably lower than in wild fish
(Mandich et al., 2004), they were sufficient in stimulating and sustaining vitellogenesis.
472 Opposite to the well-known and acknowledged role of E2 and 11-KT in the gametogenic and
maturation process of fish, few studies have dealt with the role of intermediate metabolites
474 of the steroidogenic pathway. For instance, in the congeneric Japanese yellowtail (*Seriola*

quinqneradiata), it was reported that the synthesis of E2 passed through the conversion of $\Delta 4$
476 (Rahman et al., 2002), while in two other teleost species, the red seabream (*Pagrus major*) and
the bambooleaf wrasse (*Pseudolabrus sieboldi*) the main substrate for the biosynthesis of E2
478 came from E1 via Adrenosterone conversion, instead of T (Ohta et al., 2001; Ohta et al., 2002).
Although it remains to be verified in greater amberjack, a more complex than a T-to-E2
480 pathway might explain our results. In fact, even though the levels of T in F1 females were low
and unchanged over the years, it was when all females were found in advanced vitellogenesis,
482 at five years of age, that a concomitant reduction in the concentrations of E1 was evident.
Furthermore, not only the steroidogenic pathway might differ during gametogenesis among
484 teleost fish, but also specific differences in the development of the BPG axis do exist
(Okuzawa, 2002). For instance, in the black carp (*Mylopharngodon piceus*) the acquisition of
486 competence of the pituitary and gonads to respond to hormonal stimulation was demonstrated
to occur in synchrony in the two organs (Gur et al., 2000). In red seabream, on the other hand,
488 the administration of GnRH α increased plasma levels of luteinizing hormone (Lh), but did not
cause a gonadal response in 12-month-old fish, while the same treatment induced vitellogenesis
490 and ovulation in 16-month-old fish, suggesting distinct timing of acquisition of competency
for pituitary and gonads (Kumakura et al., 2003). Considering all these data together, the
492 present results indicate a partial lack of competence of the BPG axis resulting in reduced
aromatization of precursors of E2 and the progression of vitellogenesis in young females of
494 this species.

The main steroids controlling spermatogenesis in fishes are 11-KT and its precursor T
496 (Schulz and Miura, 2002; Schulz et al., 2010). In wild greater amberjack in the Mediterranean,
the highest recorded levels of T were found in males with mature testes having sperm cysts in
498 advanced spermatogenesis, as well as free spermatozoa in the luminal space, whereas 11-KT
reached maximum values when the testicular lobules were greatly enlarged and entirely

500 occupied by spermatozoa (Mandich et al., 2004). In F1 males here, the mean T plasma
concentration was lower than in wild individuals (Mandich et al., 2004), but comparable with
502 those of both captive-reared and hatchery-produced breeders examined during the reproductive
season elsewhere (Jerez et al., 2018; Zupa et al., 2017b). Furthermore, T plasma levels
504 decreased gradually over consecutive reproductive seasons, concomitantly with increasing
concentrations of 11-KT; these levels of 11-KT were two- to four-fold higher compared to
506 captive fish and resembled those found in the wild during the reproductive season (Mandich et
al., 2004; Zupa et al., 2017b). We conducted samplings at yearly intervals, thus it was not
508 possible to monitor seasonal variations of steroids in relation to gonadal development. Even
so, plasma levels of T and 11-KT were at the highest concentration in 3- and 4-yo males, which
510 exhibited an analogous reproductive stage to males in the wild that were categorized as ripe,
suggesting the correct progression of the gametogenic process. In addition, a prominent role
512 in both sperm maturation and motility is played by progestins (Schulz et al., 2010; Tubbs and
Thomas, 2008). In adult greater amberjack (Mandich et al., 2004), as well as in yellowtail
514 kingfish (Poortenaar et al., 2001), low levels of 17,20 β -P were found and were associated to a
partial inability to reach full maturation, as evidenced by the lack of sperm hydration and the
516 ability to obtain sperm by abdominal pressure, and the presence of milt of high density and low
GSI (Zupa et al., 2017a). The generally low concentration of 17,20 β -P in the plasma of F1
518 males seemingly reflected these previous results, and when lower GSI values and higher sperm
density than those of wild fish were also considered, it may conceivably point out to a partial
520 inability to produce expressible milt and also explain the absence of fertilization during the
spawning events.

522 Due to the scarcity of spontaneous spawning in cultured greater amberjack (Jerez et al.,
2006; Sarih et al., 2018) and the reported reproductive dysfunctions in this species (Corriero et
524 al., 2021a; Corriero et al., 2021b; Pousis et al., 2018; Zupa et al., 2017b), the production of

fertilized eggs still remains one of the main bottlenecks for the expansion of its culture. Given
526 the extensive observations that greater amberjack fail to undergo oocyte maturation, ovulation,
and spawning reliably in land-based tanks (Fakriadis et al., 2020a; Fakriadis et al., 2020b; Jerez
528 et al., 2018; Sarih et al., 2018), in the present study 4- and 5-yo fish were induced to spawn
following the established methodology for wild-caught, captive-reared individuals of this
530 species. In captive-reared greater amberjack broodstocks, induction of spawning through
GnRHa administration has been effective in increasing egg production (Fakriadis et al., 2019;
532 Fakriadis et al., 2020a; Fakriadis et al., 2020b; Fernández-Palacios et al., 2015). Similarly, in
F1 individuals from the Atlantic Ocean, GnRHa administration induced successfully multiple
534 spawning over a prolonged period of time, using either sustained-release implants or multiple
injections (Jerez et al., 2018; Sarih et al., 2018). In contrast, in the present study treating F1
536 breeders from the Mediterranean Sea with GnRHa implants was not successful, since only two
spawns were obtained from probably only one 5-yo female in a period of 15 days, with no
538 fertilized eggs, whereas no spawns at all were obtained from 4-yo fish. This dichotomy in
results might be explained by a combination of different factors. The main goal of the present
540 study was to identify the first age of maturation of hatchery-produced greater amberjack and
evaluate their reproductive capacity. It is customary to define individuals as sexually mature
542 using the presence of vitellogenic oocytes in the ovary as a criterion of spawning capability.
This has also been done previously with greater amberjack (Marino et al., 1995), thus, the 4-
544 and 5-yo F1 females examined in the present study were considered to have completed puberty.
However, although the precise age of F1 breeders used from the Atlantic Ocean was not clearly
546 defined, the authors indicated that greater amberjack induced to spawn in May 2015 were born
between 2005 and 2009, which implies that the youngest fish was at least 6-yo (Jerez et al.,
548 2018). In many teleost species, young individuals might undergo gonadal development, but
eventually skip the reproductive season and reabsorb their Vg follicles, in order to redirect and

550 reinvest the energy in somatic growth (Rideout and Tomkiewicz, 2011). Therefore, due to the
extensive follicular atresia recorded in the ovary of 4-yo females, and the poor reproductive
552 output (*i.e.* fecundity and fertilization) after the GnRHa therapy in 5-yo females, it seems
doubtful that F1 generation Mediterranean greater amberjack can be induced to spawn
554 successfully at this age. On the contrary, natural spawning was reported for 2-yo hatchery-
produced F1 breeders produced and reared in Japan (Kawabe et al., 1996), as well as for 3-yo
556 females in the Canary Islands (Sarih et al., 2018). This vast discrepancy in the age of maturity
and spawning capability might result from the worldwide distribution of this species and the
558 existence of distinct genetic populations (Gold and Richardson, 1998; Hasegawa et al., 2020;
Šegvić-Bubić et al., 2016) adapted to different environmental conditions -varying between
560 temperate and sub-tropical regions. Therefore, further investigation is necessary, in order to
examine if the genetic differences that can be identified in stocks of greater amberjack
562 inhabiting different geographical areas, such as the Mediterranean Sea and the Atlantic Ocean
(Šegvić-Bubić et al., 2016), may correlate with the observed differences in reproductive
564 function, already reported and proposed earlier (Corriero et al., 2021a).

566 **Conclusions**

The results obtained in the present study indicate that male hatchery-produced F1 greater
568 amberjack mature as 3-yo as observed in wild males, albeit with smaller gonad size. On the
contrary, females seem to mature at a later age than in the wild, also with a smaller gonad size.
570 Although 5-yo females have a normal ovarian histological appearance based on ovarian
biopsies, spawning in response to GnRHa treatment was not effective, contrary to what has
572 been shown with wild-caught captive-reared broodstock, but also with hatchery-produced
broodstocks from the Atlantic Ocean. More studies are necessary to evaluate (a) if reproductive
574 function may improve with age, (b) if different hatchery-produced broodstocks may perform

576 better reproductively and to establish an effective protocol for spawning induction of hatchery-
produced greater amberjack from the Mediterranean Sea.

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828 **Figure legends**

830 **Figure 1.** Water temperature profile (°C) in the sea cages where the two populations of
832 hatchery-produced greater amberjack were maintained during the time of the experiment
(SOUDA, 2017-2018 in Souda Bay, Crete, Greece; ARGO, 2017-2022 in Argosaronikos
834 Fish farms S.A., Salamina Island, Greece). Shaded sections mark the expected period of
reproductive maturation and spawning of greater amberjack in the Mediterranean Sea.
Fish were sampled every year in June at the expected peak of the spawning season.

Figure 2. Mean (\pm SEM) **A.** body weight (BW), **B.** total length (TL) and **C.** gonadosomatic
836 index (GSI) of hatchery-produced greater amberjack males and females reared in sea
cages from 1 to 5 years of age (2018-2022). Fish were sampled every year in June at the
838 expected peak of the spawning season (See Fig. 1). Different lowercase letters indicate
statistically significant differences between years (two-way ANOVA, Tukey HSD, $P <$
840 0.05). n/a: no data obtained.

Figure 3. Microphotographs of histological sections from ovaries of hatchery-produced greater
842 amberjack males and females reared in sea cages from 1 to 5 years of age (2018-2022)
at representative stages of reproductive development. Fish were sampled every year in
844 June at the expected peak of the spawning season (See Fig. 1). **A.** Ovary of 1-year-old
(yo) female having mostly oogonia (og) and primary oocytes (po) in the lamellae. **B.**
846 Ovary of 2-yo female filled with po. **C.** Ovary of 3-yo female having early vitellogenic
oocytes (eVg). **D.** Ovary of 3-yo female with extensive stage α -atresia (α -At) of
848 vitellogenic follicles. **E.** Ovary of 4-yo females, showing eVg and advanced Vg oocytes
(Vg). **F.** Ovary of 4-yo females with massive presence of α - and β -atresia (β -At) of
850 vitellogenic follicles. **G.** Ovary of 5-yo female having oocytes at all stages of
gametogenesis, with isolated α -At follicles and oocytes at the cortical alveoli stage (ca).

852 H. Ovary of 5-yo female with β -At vitellogenic follicles. The scale bars indicate 500 μm
853 (A-H) and 100 μm (A. insert).

854 **Figure 4.** Microphotographs of histological sections from testes at representative stages of
855 reproductive development, of hatchery-produced greater amberjack males reared in sea
856 cages from 1 to 5 years of age (2018-2022). Fish were sampled every year in June at the
857 expected peak of the spawning season (See Fig. 1). **A.** Testicular section of 1-year-old
858 (yo) immature male. Spermatogonia (so) are the main cell population in the testes, with
859 the occasional presence of more advanced spermatocysts, as well as free spermatozoa
860 (sz). **B.** Early gametogenesis in a 2-yo males. Different germ cell stages, including so,
861 spermatocytes (sc), spermatids (sd), and sz were equally present in the testicular lobules.
862 **C.** Advanced spermatogenesis in 2-yo and 3-yo males, with testes displaying many
863 luminal sz and active sperm cysts in the germinal epithelium. **D.** Arrested
864 spermatogenesis in a 4-yo male, with vast numbers of spermatozoa present in the lumen,
865 and only a few residual spermatocysts in the germinal epithelium. Black scale bar = 500
866 μm .

Figure 5. Percentage frequency (%) of gonadal maturation stages of hatchery-produced greater
867 amberjack sampled in June of each year (2018-2022, See Fig. 1). **A.** Females of 1 and 2
868 years of age had immature ovaries containing only primary oocytes (Po). At 3 and 4
869 years of age, females at the stage of advanced vitellogenesis (Vg) or with extensive
870 follicular atresia (At) were also present. **B.** Males showed variable stages of
871 spermatogenesis in their testes, from the first year of the study. In addition to immature
872 males (IM) with testes filled with spermatogonia, some males were in early
873 spermatogenesis (EG) with an equal presence of all germ cell stages (*i.e.* spermatogonia,
874 spermatocytes, spermatids, and spermatozoa) in the testes. At 3 and 4 years of age, all
875 males were either at the advanced spermatogenesis stage (AS) with large numbers of
876

spermatozoa in the testicular lumen, as well as many spermatocysts with developing
878 germ cells or were at the arrested spermatogenesis stage (ArS), with testes filled with
luminal spermatozoa and very few residual spermatocysts. n/a: no data obtained.

880 **Figure 6.** Mean (\pm SEM) plasma sex steroid hormone levels of testosterone (T), and 11-
ketotestosterone (11- KT) of hatchery-produced greater amberjack (3-5 years old) reared
882 in sea cages and sampled in June of each year (2020-2022, See Fig. 1). Different
lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences (Welch's ANOVA,
884 Dunnett's T3 HSD, $P < 0.05$).

Figure 7. Mean (\pm SEM) plasma sex steroid hormone levels of estrone (E1), 17β -estradiol
886 (E2), and $17,20\beta$ -dihydroxy-4-pregnen-3-one ($17,20\beta$ -P) of hatchery-produced greater
amberjack (3-5 years old) reared in sea cages and sampled in June of each year (2020-
888 2022, See Fig. 1). Different lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences
(Welch's ANOVA, Dunnett's T3 HSD, $P < 0.05$).

890 **Figure 8.** Mean (\pm SEM) plasma concentration of the sex steroid hormone **A.** Testosterone (T),
and **B.** 17β -estradiol (E2) of hatchery-produced female greater amberjack (3-5 years old)
892 according to the stage of their ovaries (see Fig. 5), *i.e.* primary oocytes (Po), advanced
vitellogenesis (Vg) or presence of extensive follicular atresia (At). Different lowercase
894 letters indicate statistically significant differences (Welch's ANOVA, Dunnett's T3
HSD, $P < 0.05$).

896 **Figure 9.** Mean (\pm SEM) sperm quality parameters of hatchery-produced male greater
amberjack (3-5 years old) reared in sea cages and sampled in June of each year (2020-
898 2022, See Fig. 1). In 2021 and 2022, the sampling was done during the selection for
spawning induction. **A.** Sperm density ($\times 10^9$ szoa ml^{-1}), **B.** Percentage (%) of motile
900 cells, progressive cells, rapid cells and straightness (STR). **C.** Curvilinear (VCL, $\mu\text{m sec}^{-1}$),
straight line (VSL, $\mu\text{m sec}^{-1}$) and average path velocity (VAP, $\mu\text{m sec}^{-1}$). Different

902 lowercase letters indicate statistically significant differences (Kruskall-Wallis test,
Dunn's HSD, $P < 0.05$). ns: not significant.

904 **Fig. 10.** Daily relative fecundity (bars, eggs kg^{-1} female) and fertilization success (circles, %)
of 5-yo hatchery-produced greater amberjack induced to spawn with GnRH α implants in
906 2022. The black arrow indicates the time of GnRH α administration.